

The Wright function

Numerical approximation and hypergeometric representation

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The Wright function

Sir. E. M. Wright

$$W(a, b | z) := \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{k! \Gamma(ak + b)}, \quad z \in \mathbb{C} \quad (1)$$

E. M. Wright, *On the coefficients of power series having exponential singularities*. J. London Math. Soc. 8 (1933), 71–79.

Motivation

Applications

- Mainardi's M-Wright function [1].

$$M_a(z) := W(-a, 1-a | -z), \quad a < 1$$

Green's function of the time-fractional diffusion equation in 1 dimension.

- Integral representation of the Prabhakar's function

$$E_{a,b}^\gamma(z) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\gamma)} \int_0^\infty e^{-t} t^{\gamma-1} W(a, b | zt) dt$$

- Generalizes Bessel, Airy, Gaussian, Error, etc. functions, their derivatives and integrals

⇒ **Computation and representation algorithms can be of general interest**

Previous results

Representation through hypergeometric functions:

- Miller and Moskowitz (1995) [2] via Meijer G function representation
- Gorenflo, Luchko and Mainardi (1999) [3] – only for rational $a > 0$ via Meijer G function representation
- Apelblat and González-Santander (2021) [4] – only for rational from first principles $a > 0$

Numerical algorithms:

- Luchko et al. [5, 6] – only the case $|b| \leq 1$.
- Aceto and Durastante – Laplace transform inversion [7]

Hypergeometric representation

Generalized Hypergeometric (GHG) function ${}_pF_q$:

$${}_pF_q \left(a_0 \dots a_{p-1}; b_0 \dots b_{q-1} \middle| z \right) := \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^r}{r!} \frac{\prod_{j=0}^{p-1} (a_j)_r}{\prod_{j=0}^{q-1} (b_j)_r} \quad (2)$$

Apelblat and González-Santander (2021) [4] demonstrate

Theorem (First HG Representation)

Suppose that $a = n/m > 0$, where n and m are co-prime natural numbers. Then

$$W(a = n/m, b | z) = \sum_{r=0}^{m-1} \frac{z^r}{r! \Gamma(b + ar)} {}_1F_{m+n} \left(1; b_0 \dots b_{n-1}, c_0 \dots c_{m-1} \middle| \frac{z^m}{n^n m^m} \right) \quad (3)$$

where

$$b_j = r/m + (b + j)/n, \quad c_j = (r + 1 + j)/m$$

Proof, I

Start from the series rearrangement

$$W(a = n/m, b|z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{n! \Gamma(an + b)} = \sum_{q=0}^{m-1} \sum_{p \geq q/m}^{\infty} \frac{z^{mp-q}}{\Gamma(mp - q + 1) \Gamma(a(mp - q) + b)}$$

since the integer n can be partitioned as $n = mp - q$ for $q = 0, \dots, m - 1$. Then

$$W(n/m, b|z) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(b)} + \sum_{r=1}^m z^r \sum_{p=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^{mp}}{\Gamma(ap + ra + b) \Gamma(mp + r + 1)}.$$

Observe that for $p = 0$ the inner series coefficient is $C_r = 1/\Gamma(ra + b)\Gamma(r + 1)$, which serves as a normalization factor. Therefore, the series transforms as

$$W(n/m, b|z) = \sum_{r=0}^m \frac{z^r}{C_r} \cdot \sum_{p=0}^{\infty} \frac{C_r}{\Gamma(n(p + r/m + b/n)) \Gamma(m(p + (r + 1)/m))} z^{mp} \quad (4)$$

Proof, II

Observe that

$$\Gamma(b + aj) = \Gamma(a(j + b/a)) = \Gamma(b) \left(\frac{b}{a}\right)_j \left(\frac{b+1}{a}\right)_j \cdots \left(\frac{b+a-1}{a}\right)_j a^{aj}$$

From eq. 4 we read off

$$b_0 = \frac{r}{m} + \frac{b}{n}, \quad c_0 = \frac{r+1}{m}$$

with increments $1/n$ and $1/m$, respectively. Therefore, finally,

$$W(a, b|z) = \sum_{r=0}^{m-1} \frac{z^r}{r! \Gamma(b + ar)} \cdot {}_1F_{m+n} \left(1; b_0 \dots b_{n-1}, c_0 \dots c_{m-1} \middle| \frac{z^m}{n^n m^m} \right).$$

Observe that for $r = m - 1$ $c_1 = 1$. Therefore, the GHG functions reduce to ${}_0F_{m+n-1}$.

New Results

Theorem (Second HG Representation)

For $b \leq 1$ and $n \leq m$ non-negative co-prime integers

$$W(a = -n/m, b | z) = \sum_{r=0}^{m-1} \frac{z^r}{r! \Gamma(b + ar)} {}_{n+1}F_m \left(1, b'_0 \dots b'_{n-1}; c_0 \dots c_{m-1} \middle| \frac{(-)^n z^m}{n^n m^m} \right) \quad (5)$$

where

$$b'_j = 1 + r/m - (b + j)/n \quad c_j = (r + 1 + j)/m$$

Proof

Suppose that $b < 1$ and let

$$W(-n/m, b|z) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(b)} + \sum_{r=1}^m \frac{z^r}{C_r} \sum_{p=0}^{\infty} \frac{C_r}{\Gamma(-np - rn/m + b)} \frac{z^{mp}}{\Gamma(mp + r + 1)}$$

By the Gamma reflection formula

$$\frac{1}{\Gamma(-np - rn/m + b)} = \frac{(-1)^{np} \Gamma\left(\frac{nr}{m} + np - b + 1\right)}{\Gamma\left(b - \frac{nr}{m}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{nr}{m} - b + 1\right)} \quad (6)$$

Therefore,

$$W(-n/m, b|z) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(b)} + \sum_{r=1}^m \frac{z^r}{C_r} \sum_{p=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{np} C_r \Gamma\left(\frac{nr}{m} + np - b + 1\right) z^{mp}}{\Gamma\left(\frac{nr}{m} - b + 1\right) \Gamma(m(p + (r + 1)/m))}$$

Read off the parameters

$$b'_j = 1 - (-r/m + (b + j)/n) = 1 + r/m - (b + j)/n.$$

Integral representation

Integral representation

Starting from the Hankel's formula

$$\frac{1}{\Gamma(\mu)} = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{H_{a-}} \frac{e^{\xi}}{\xi^{\mu}} d\xi$$

branch cut at $\arg \xi < 0$, it can be shown that

$$W(a, b|z) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{H_{a-}} \frac{e^{\xi+z\xi^{-a}}}{\xi^b} d\xi \quad (7)$$

Polynomial representation

For $n = -a$ and $b = m$, $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ by residue

$$W(-n, m|z) = \text{Res}(ker(\xi), \xi = 0) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(m)} \left\{ \left(\frac{d}{d\xi} \right)^{m-1} e^{\xi + z\xi^n} \right\} \Big|_{\xi=0}$$

Explicit computation by application of Faá di Bruno's formula:

$$W(-n, m|z) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(m)} B_{m-1} \left(g'(0), \dots, g^{(m-1)}(0) \right) \quad (8)$$

where $B_m(\dots)$ are the complete exponential Bell polynomials and $g(\xi) = \xi + z\xi^n$:

$$B_m \left(g'(0), \dots, g^{(m)}(0) \right) = \begin{vmatrix} \binom{m-1}{0} g'(0) & \binom{m-2}{1} g''(0) & \dots & \binom{m-1}{m-1} g^{(m)}(0) \\ -1 & \binom{m-2}{1} g'(0) & \dots & \binom{m-2}{m-2} g^{(m-1)}(0) \\ 0 & -1 & \dots & \binom{m-3}{m-3} g^{(m-3)}(0) \\ & & \dots & \\ 0 & \dots & -1 & \binom{0}{0} g'(0) \end{vmatrix}$$

Polynomial representation

$$m = 1 :$$

$$1, z + 1$$

$$m = 2 :$$

$$\frac{1}{2}, \frac{2z + 1}{2}, \frac{(z + 1)^2}{2}$$

$$m = 3 :$$

$$\frac{1}{6}, \frac{6z + 1}{6}, \frac{6z + 1}{6}, \frac{(z + 1)^3}{6}$$

$$m = 4$$

$$\frac{1}{24}, \frac{24z + 1}{24}, \frac{24z + 1}{24}, \frac{12z^2 + 12z + 1}{24}, \frac{(z + 1)^4}{24}$$

$$m = 5 :$$

$$\frac{1}{120}, \frac{120z + 1}{120}, \frac{120z + 1}{120}, \frac{60z + 1}{120}, \frac{60z^2 + 20z + 1}{120}, \frac{(z + 1)^5}{120}$$

Mixed representation

Theorem (Third HG representation)

Suppose that a and b are rational parameters and $b \geq 1$ and $|a| \leq 1$. Define the polynomial $P_b(-a, z)$ by the integral recursion

$$P_b(-a, z) = \int_0^z P_{b-a}(-a, x) dx + c_{b-1}, \quad (9)$$

where $c_{b-1} = 1/(b-1)!$ if b is an integer and 0 otherwise. Furthermore, define $P_0(z, -a) := 1$ and for $b < 0$ assign $P_b(z, -a) := 0$ identically. Then

$$W(a = -n/m, b|z) = \sum_{r=0}^{m-1} \frac{z^r}{r! \Gamma(b+ar)} \cdot {}_{n+1}F_m \left(1, b'_0 \dots b'_{n-1}; c_0 \dots c_{m-1} \middle| \frac{(-)^n z^m}{n^n m^m} \right) + P_b(-a, z) \quad (10)$$

where m and n are co-prime numbers.

Approximation by quadratures

Derivation

For the ray part

$$ker_{AB} = \frac{e^{\frac{-ia\delta}{r^a}z} + e^{i\delta r - ib\delta}}{r^b}$$

$$ker_{ED} = \frac{e^{\frac{ia\delta}{r^a}z} + e^{-i\delta r + ib\delta}}{r^b}$$

$$ker_{AB} - ker_{ED} = \frac{2ie^{\cos(\delta)r + \frac{\cos(a\delta)z}{r^a}} \sin\left(\frac{\sin(a\delta)z}{r^a} + \sin(\delta)r - b\delta\right)}{r^b}$$

$$W(a, b|z) = \underbrace{I_{AB} + I_{DE}}_{I_r} + \underbrace{I_{BCD}}_{I_{arc}}$$

$$I_r(\epsilon) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{\epsilon}^{\infty} \frac{e^{\frac{\cos(\pi a)z}{r^a} - r} \sin\left(\frac{\sin(\pi a)z}{r^a} + \pi b\right)}{r^b} dr$$

(11)

Derivation

For the arc part

$$\ker_{BCD} = \frac{ie^{-ia\varphi}z + \epsilon e^{i\varphi - ib\varphi}}{\epsilon^b} e^{i\varphi} \epsilon$$

$$\ker_{BCD} = \frac{ie^{\epsilon \cos(\varphi) + \frac{\cos(a\varphi)z}{\epsilon^a}} \cos\left(\frac{-\sin(a\varphi)z}{\epsilon^a} + \epsilon \sin(\varphi) - b\varphi + \varphi\right)}{\epsilon^b}$$

$$- \frac{\epsilon e^{\epsilon \cos(\varphi) + \frac{\cos(a\varphi)z}{\epsilon^a}} \sin\left(\frac{-\sin(a\varphi)z}{\epsilon^a} + \epsilon \sin(\varphi) - b\varphi + \varphi\right)}{\epsilon^b}$$

$$W(a, b|z) = \underbrace{I_{AB} + I_{DE}}_{I_{ray}} + \underbrace{I_{BCD}}_{P_\epsilon}$$

$$P_\epsilon = \frac{\epsilon^{1-b}}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} e^{\epsilon \cos \varphi + \cos(a\varphi)z/\epsilon^a} \cos\left(-\sin(a\varphi)z/\epsilon^a + \epsilon \sin \varphi + (1-b)\varphi\right) d\varphi \quad (12)$$

\implies for $b < 1$ $\epsilon \rightarrow 0 \implies P_\epsilon \rightarrow 0$

Phase Analysis

We look for the set where the phase of the kernel

$$ker(\xi) = \frac{e^{\xi+z\xi^{-a}}}{\xi^b} d\xi$$

$$\frac{d}{d\xi} (z/\xi^a + \xi) \Big|_{\xi=\xi_0} = \left(-\frac{az}{\xi^{a+1}} + 1 \right) \Big|_{\xi=\xi_0} = 0 \implies \xi_0 = \sqrt[a+1]{az}$$

is stationary to first order.

The Hölder exponent β

$$\beta \simeq h(\xi) := \xi \frac{d}{d\xi} \log \left(\frac{e^{\xi \frac{z}{\xi^a} + \xi}}{\xi^b} \right) = -\frac{az}{\xi^a} + \xi - b$$

At the origin

\implies for $a < 0$ $\beta = h(\xi) \Big|_{\xi=0} = -b$. If $b < 1$ – integrable singularity $\implies \epsilon = 0$.

$\implies a > 0$ – appearance of an essential singularity at the origin $\implies \epsilon = \sqrt[a+1]{|az|}$.

Computation table

$\begin{matrix} \backslash \\ \text{b} \end{matrix} \quad \text{a}$	$a < 0$	$a = 0$	$a > 0$
$b \leq 1$	$W(a, b z) = I_r(0)$	$W(a, b z) = \frac{e^z}{\Gamma(b)}$	$W(a, b z) = I_u(\epsilon^a) + P(\epsilon)$
$b = 1$	$W(a, b z) = I_r(0) + 1$		
$b > 1$	$W(a, b z) = I_r(\epsilon) + P(\epsilon)$		

$$I_r(\epsilon) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{\epsilon}^{\infty} \frac{\sin\left(\frac{\sin(\pi a)z}{r^a} + \pi b\right)}{r^b} e^{\frac{\cos(\pi a)z}{r^a} - r} dr, \quad \epsilon = {}^{a+1}\sqrt{|az|}$$

$$I_u(\epsilon) = \frac{1}{\pi a} \int_{\epsilon}^{\infty} \frac{\sin(\sin(\pi a)z/u + \pi b)}{u^{\frac{b-1}{a}+1}} e^{\cos(\pi a)z/u - u^{1/a}} du, \quad r^a \mapsto u$$

$$P(\epsilon) = \frac{\epsilon^{1-b}}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} e^{\epsilon \cos \varphi + \cos(a\varphi)z/\epsilon^a} \cos(-\sin(a\varphi)z/\epsilon^a + \epsilon \sin \varphi + (1-b)\varphi) d\varphi, \quad \epsilon = {}^{a+1}\sqrt{|az|}$$

Examples

Bessel J_0 and $J_{1/2}$ functions

M-Wright function

Mainardi's M-Wright[1].

$$M_a(z) = W(-a, 1-a | -z)$$

a	$M_a(z)$
+0	e^{-z}
1/2	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} e^{-z^2/4}$
1/3	$\sqrt[3]{3^2} Ai(z/\sqrt[3]{3})$

Examples: GHG reduction

■ $a = 1/3$

$$W(1/3, b|z) = \frac{{}_0F_3\left(-; b + \frac{2}{3}, \frac{4}{3}, \frac{5}{3}; \frac{z^3}{27}\right) z^2}{2\Gamma\left(b + \frac{2}{3}\right)} + \frac{{}_0F_3\left(-, b + \frac{1}{3}, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{4}{3}; \frac{z^3}{27}\right) z}{\Gamma\left(b + \frac{1}{3}\right)} + \frac{{}_0F_3\left(-; b, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{2}{3}; \frac{z^3}{27}\right)}{\Gamma(b)} \quad (13)$$

■ $a = -1/3, b \leq 1$

$$W(-1/3, b|z) = \frac{{}_1F_2\left(\frac{5}{3} - b; \frac{4}{3}, \frac{5}{3}; -\frac{z^3}{27}\right) z^2}{2\Gamma\left(b - \frac{2}{3}\right)} + \frac{{}_1F_2\left(\frac{4}{3} - b; \frac{2}{3}, \frac{4}{3}; -\frac{z^3}{27}\right) z}{\Gamma\left(b - \frac{1}{3}\right)} + \frac{{}_1F_2\left(1 - b; \frac{1}{3}, \frac{2}{3}, -\frac{z^3}{27}\right)}{\Gamma(b)} \quad (14)$$

Examples: GHG reduction

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Particular cases

■ $a = -1/3, b = 1/3$

$$W(-1/3, 1/3 | -z) = -\frac{\left(I_{2/3}\left(\frac{2z^{3/2}}{3^{3/2}}\right) - I_{-2/3}\left(\frac{2z^{3/2}}{3^{3/2}}\right)\right)z}{3} = \frac{z}{\sqrt{3}\pi} K_{2/3}\left(\frac{2z^{3/2}}{3^{3/2}}\right) = -\sqrt[3]{3} \operatorname{Ai}'\left(\frac{z}{\sqrt[3]{3}}\right) \quad (15)$$

■ $a = -1/3, b = 2/3$

$$W(-1/3, 2/3 | -z) = \frac{I_{-1/3}\left(\frac{2z^{3/2}}{3^{3/2}}\right)\sqrt{z}}{\sqrt{3}} - \frac{I_{1/3}\left(\frac{2z^{3/2}}{3^{3/2}}\right)\sqrt{z}}{\sqrt{3}} = \frac{K_{1/3}\left(\frac{2z^{3/2}}{3^{3/2}}\right)\sqrt{z}}{\pi} = \sqrt[3]{3^2} \operatorname{Ai}\left(z/\sqrt[3]{3}\right) \quad (16)$$

Particular cases

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$$\frac{z}{\sqrt{3}\pi} K_{2/3}\left(\frac{2z^{3/2}}{3^{3/2}}\right) = -\sqrt[3]{3} \operatorname{Ai}'\left(\frac{z}{\sqrt[3]{3}}\right) \quad (15)$$

■ $a = -1/3, b = 2/3$

$$W(-1/3, 2/3 | -z) = \frac{I_{-1/3}\left(\frac{2z^{3/2}}{3^{3/2}}\right) \sqrt{z}}{\sqrt{3}} - \frac{I_{1/3}\left(\frac{2z^{3/2}}{3^{3/2}}\right) \sqrt{z}}{\sqrt{3}} =$$

$$\frac{K_{1/3}\left(\frac{2z^{3/2}}{3^{3/2}}\right) \sqrt{z}}{\pi} = \sqrt[3]{3^2} \operatorname{Ai}\left(z/\sqrt[3]{3}\right) \quad (16)$$

Summary

- Demonstrated a new class of polynomial representations of the Wright function
- Demonstrated a new mixed representation for negative rationals
- Demonstrated quadrature approximation for all parameter ranges

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